

Determinants of Unemployment: A social problem in Hyderabad Region Sindh–Pakistan

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Abstract: This article is set out to investigate the determinants of unemployment in Hyderabad region –Sindh Province –Pakistan. Unemployment as a social issue is associated with the various factors such as overpopulation, low paid system, force work face, financial crisis, job vacancy, mismatch of skills and education, migration, labor –market and so forth. The quantitative method employed for the study, and focus group interviews structured out among male and female respondents. Hence, the study revealed that unemployment is the core social problem of Hyderabad region resulting in frustration and upset within the social life of the individuals. A sample of 260 respondents was taken from the targeted population, mainly focuses on the close-ended questionnaire. Further, the raw data is analyzed through (SPSS) software, and other techniques used for analyzing the statistical data Non-parametric tests, ANOVA, reliability, Linear Regression, and correlation Chi-Square test based on the collected raw data from individuals.

Key words: individuals, unemployment, education, population and migration

I. Introduction

Pakistan -The Islamic republic country created on 14 August 1947, and Sindh as the province of Pakistan is facing an unemployment issue for many decades especially Hyderabad region has been confronting it for a long time. Presently, the ratio of unemployed individuals in Pakistan is more than 12 percent inclusion of 113 million persons (Nizami.S; 2010). As per the most recent labor survey for 2008-09, the unemployment rate in flated to 55% from 52% unemployment rate as 15 percent. (Khalil; 1999). Hyderabad is richly industrial and agricultural zone. Hence, the pleasures of Individual reply on the various items that ingrain in health, income, social status, moral values, job characteristics, worldly leisure, security, market status, working hours and liberty. In addition to them, the most effective factor in life experience is unemployment in a social life. The overall, unemployment is social issue, and it occurs when people are without jobs. Unemployment means people are able to work and actively finding job but fail to get a job

(Ahn et al, 2004). Meanwhile the educated and less educated individuals seek work for survival in a society. Meanwhile there is no work job for such the individuals then they are recognized as unemployed figure of a civil society. (Ahsan khan 2012) such a study is related to unemployment. In addition to this, unemployment is the outcomes of over population. Each civil society has some jobless figures. "While some youths enter the labor force so as to seek out a job right away; workers may leave their jobs to find out new works or stay at home rearing offspring and other intend to go on the strike. Whereas some other reasoning from illness for a long time. Besides to this, some figures are uneducated or lacking skills for any task. In other words, unemployment is mainly related with such the individuals establishing the labor potency of the realm, who are able-bodied and keen to labor, but are not advantageously laboring. As stated by Beleva (1997), "Unemployment is a main reason to monetary feat in a market economy. Nevertheless, it carries out various negative social and economic consequences. They are further most discernible in developing or inefficiently operating labour markets. The larger and longer the unemployment, the deeper and more intricate are the social and economic difficulties it reasons in society" As per Bureau of Labor Statistics: "The unemployment rate signifies the figure of jobless as a per cent of the labor force." Unemployment comprises individuals- are not engaged, the then enthusiastically seeking for labor or waiting to return to work. Unemployment is the basic issue presenting effectively within the entire nations all the globe."

According to IMF report (2008) 'unemployment is assessed yearly as ratio of that labor force that can't seek out work'

International Labor Organization (1996) states that unemployment is the condition stated as far away from labor or requiring an occupation incessantly probing into it in the preceding four week or jobless (age 16 or above) however that is accessible to join task in the next two weeks. Individual swillingly do not need to do task whole period while the retired persons, pupils and youngsters are no encompassed with jobless group. In a brief, unemployment presents a position when individuals are enthusiastic and capable to perform a duty, but cannot attain the preferred job. But the failures in achievement that give a birth so many social problems such as criminality, poverty, suicide and others. Simultaneously, it affects the workers, their families because they have no jobs, income and production for survival in a human society despite the potential to work under any circumstance.

However, unemployment is social problem of human society, and unemployment persons who have capabilities and the determination to do labor, but there is lack of occasions to gain occupations that are in the kind of unemployed persons. When unemployment high resources are wasted, people's profits are dejected. Keeping in view that the individuals of Hyderabad division being well-educated and skillful in every field of work, but there is less opportunity to avail any sort of work. For better-understanding the determinants of unemployment as mentioned below: -

Population growth

The overall world general population depends on agrarian society, and residing in exurban regions of the countries of the world. The population can highly rely on cultivation of land for survival in human society. Besides to this, agrarian society represents traditional strategies as much of the population survive on such the strategy for decades. Hence, that lacks alternative choice in the market. Therefore, unemployed people are at a great number in Hyderabad that would be a big threat for the province. Irrespective to this, the populace of Hyderabad is extremely raising at rate of 2.2% as per statistical survey currently. The population rises, but the state regime cannot offer occupations to all the inhabitants (Phulpotoe at., 2012). The major reasons for increasing of populace like migration, dearth of consciousness; illiteracy, early marriage, yearning for son, and so forth.

Poor education system

Since the education system of Hyderabad –Sindh remained as poor after the partition because the most of educated class had been migrated to India. Unfortunately, none of the government has yet taken any serious action for improvement and better education to the citizens of Hyderabad. On account of it, many individuals left getting education owing to poor education system in Hyderabad. Besides to this, technical and non-technical institutions have still been imparting dull and poor quality of education and producing such category of the individuals who roam for job that they lack skills and experiences.

Energy crisis

Broadly, natural resources and atomic power as other generating resources are available in Hyderabad division, but there remains an issue of energy crisis. This is because of improper planning regarding energy issue in Hyderabad division. Meanwhile the government remained the failure in providing energy and reducing crisis promptly for the public of the division.

Low rate of industrial growth

In Sindh especially in Hyderabad division, a low industrial rate as compared to other regions of Pakistan. Henceforth, Hyderabad has a rare industry and showing less opportunities for unemployed individuals.

Uses of advanced technology

An obsolete technology rather than an advanced technology has mostly been brought into use in Hyderabad division. In addition to this, an advanced technology can render the enumerable facilities thus; it produces a great loss for individuals who become jobless in a human society.

Mechanization of agriculture

Sindh is an agricultural rich, and has pre-partition agricultural system which is based on old structural mechanization and producing a great ratio of unemployment in Hyderabad division. Henceforth, such an old technology remains obsolete for the individuals of a civil society.

Reduction in foreign employment

Simply, the individuals of Hyderabad division confront with the various social issues such illiteracy, ill-health, criminality and others, such the facts resulted the failures in capturing foreign market for production of unemployment in human society. Hence the individuals do not have any work for survival in society.

Literacy and Illiteracy ratio in Hyderabad division

Explicitly, literacy and illiteracy ratio is recognized as unsatisfactory and producing unemployment owing to the failures in provision of jobs to the individuals in a civil society. In addition to lacking skills and technical strategies for that reason the most of such persons are unemployed in a civil society. Hence, the unemployed persons both illiterate or literate being increased and the government failed to avail jobs to the individuals of Hyderabad division.

Rural and Urban migration

Migration is social problem of human beings in society. The majority of individuals migrate from rural to urban regions for maintenance and survival strategies in society. As the individuals resort to migration for employment instead of unemployment that is reason affecting the lives of individuals in rural regions

Political instability

Political instability is a social factor in Hyderabad division producing no more interest and attraction for foreign investment. Thus, instability weakens society, then, the investors avoid investing the resources and bringing no more development. Hence, unemployment increases in a civil society.

Lack of skill strategies

Individuals of Hyderabad division lack in skill strategies because of the different reasons, some individuals are less-educated or illiterate figures and untrained in professional as well technical work.

Nepotism and favoritism

Nepotism and favoritism are such components of human society that the individuals practice since the birth of the social world for the benefits of survival in society. The most of unemployed or under-employed persons

confront with the factors meanwhile they fail to gain job because they lack approaches and preferences. The preference and approaches given those who have the components of nepotism and favoritism while skilled and educated as well technical fit individuals remain the failures in gaining job, and resorting to frustration in society Thus, the deserving individuals remain jobless in human society.

High age of retirement

Pakistani government has fixed the employees 60 years age of retirement. Thus, higher age rate of retirement brought difficulty and closing the doors for services of a long period of service; therefore, the individuals become unable to gain the suitable jobs in a society.

Types of unemployment

There are the different types of unemployment ingrained in seasonal unemployment, agricultural unemployment, technological and frictional unemployment; industrial unemployment, cyclical unemployment; educational unemployment and so on.

Seasonal unemployment

As many businesses who are seasonal and impacting upon unemployment. In peak season companies hires more individuals while in off season many workers are laid off which creates seasonal unemployment. (C.n Shankar Rao introduction to sociology), as stated that seasonal unemployment is associated with agriculture sector during the off-season many laborers will have to spend their times without any work. In some industries such as sugar, woolen and ice factories, workers get jobs only for a certain period of the year or in a particular season. When the season is over; they don't get work in the factories, and they will have to wait for the next season to come so as to find the same work.

Agricultural unemployment

However, the two main constituents which yield unemployment in agrarian area. The first, implementation of modern technology resulted in reduction the demand and prerequisite of farm work. there are two main factors which produce unemployment in agriculture sector, and second reply on the employment detached individuals cannot be re-employed by other monetary regions owing to poverty –stricken, less education and lack of skills for working in industries meanwhile they lack sufficient incomes to initiate own business setting up to break the chain of unemployment. Agricultural unemployment is on account of the number of factors like the very seasonal nature of agricultural work; the decay of cottage industries; lack of demand for homemade production; insufficient of alternative work in the rural areas and sub-division of land holdings.

Technological and frictional unemployment

Frictional unemployment is a type which will be present always as it covers only those who are temporarily unemployed.

However, friction sometimes takes place in technological field on account of unemployment owing to an imbalance between supply of labor and the demand for customers while there is constantly shifting from one product to another; it becomes difficult for workers to catch up with choices, tastes and nature of work as per own demand.

Structural Unemployment

This is a type of unemployment which occurs when enough jobs are not available to match person skills

Such type of unemployment as stated in Hyderabad division because educated and less educated individuals require jobs, but on such number the jobs are not available for the individuals in region, despite of some extent information regarding such jobs.

Industrial unemployment

Hyderabad division has countable industries as compared to foreign industrial zones. Thus, such industries provide less opportunities to the individuals owing to strange infrastructures and policies that is why the most of time, workers go on strike for their rights.

Cyclical unemployment

This type of unemployment varies with economic conditions. Like when economy contracts organizations lay off workers resulting in high unemployment. Hence, there is complexity in the trade cycle within commercial universe meanwhile the changes of low and high in the business set up for that factor there takes place unemployment on the result of decreasing of trade factor in commercial unemployment.

Educational unemployment

Generally, it is type of unemployment which is closely linked with job opportunities and the system of Education in a civil society.

II. Review of literature

Explicitly and implicitly much has been discussed about unemployment in Pakistan, as the vast literature is available for such an issue, and remained a central focus of the public in the country. Hence, the various studies related it indirectly or directly. Unemployment is a major issue in Hyderabad division, and the rich in resources. Besides to his, the different determinants resort the individuals to such slots, and resulting frustration and violent behaviors and so forth. Unemployed person is such an individual who possesses ability and willing to perform any sort of task, but not being able to acquire job opportunity in a civil society is recognized as unemployed person. However, In Pakistani society, study revealed that more than 30 lac persons are stated as unemployed in the country (Malik et al., 2011). In Pakistan, the educated individuals face higher rate of unemployment (Qayyum, 2007). Unemployment is a big challenge for the public of Sindh-Pakistan. Hence, the migration resulted on loss of agricultural –based employment on account of paucity and shortage of Water facilities in Indus River. Similarity, water- logging and salinity of soil increase the erosion and degradation the capacity of the earth from the fertile perspectives (Nasser Mammon et al. 2008). As the various reasons which have destroyed the entire infrastructure of a system like poor water –distribution and management of water resources; water –logging, salinity and erosions in the earth; unsatisfactory constructions; outdated technologies and machines; obsolete policies and strategies for agricultural development for survival perspectives (Waqas Qayyum et al. 2008, Hans F. Stenholm et al. 2004). The obsolete policies of the Government remained failure for development of human lives and provision of employment to the individuals of Hyderabad division. Further, socio-sickness apparently ruined the energy of human beings for survival and making miserable lives. In addition to lacking the facilities of education and availability of job opportunities stated as an issue for the public; unemployment is increasing swiftly in the public (Hafiz zee Shan sub Hani 2008) (Hafiz Rahman 2009). Degradation of land and shortage of water exhorted the individuals for the self-employed agriculture based employment (Alina Baber et al. 2013). The failures in production and attainable targets of agriculture work resulted inappropriate benefits of individuals causing unemployment in society directly or indirectly (Farooq 2010). Individuals remained unemployed instead of the various efforts for success through national progress; and the rate of unemployment is determined as a high level in a social life (Ghanghro. N2012). Human integration in migration context of labour market recognized as an objective over all developing the unemployment in society (Bari, H.S 2014). The serious economic problem faced by government and nation failing to provide employment to citizens due to the heavy expenditure of government state. Individuals confront with the unemployment issue in a civil society (Alam. A p no 67). Unemployment rates become law at regional and national levels, meanwhile infrastructure of the different companies sometimes downsize and producing less opportunities for jobs. In rare cases, dispute of employees with owner of companies resulted as losing jobs and exhorted the individual to seek jobs somewhere for survival in a society. The job is supposed to be a specific reason for the basic strategies for survival on the earth, and the individuals acquire money for survival in a civil society (Diana Kendal book sociology in our time), the defective educational system and obsolete technology create unemployment among the individuals of human society (William j. Moran 2014). The failures in application of resources properly resulted as unemployment increasing vastly. Apart from this, the various speculative domains are employed for measuring the factors of unemployment such as the work pursuit patterns is exposed by Mortensen (1970) and Lippman and McCall (1976). As per such the pattern, the unemployment replies upon work offer and work recognition. The work

acceptance relies on education, working experience, skills of labour, and the required situation of native places of respective regions. Acero (1993) stated few determinants of unemployment are interrelated with definite work exploration and the job within the market continuing to change with respect to nature of job of workers. Sometimes, it happens because of the heterogeneity of nature of workers; other job opportunities, the cost of training, and lack of perfect information. Assaad et al. (2000) studied the different elements of unemployment, and related with the work within market. Unemployment is increasing with constant rate. The educated individuals affected and the entry in the private sector. At the same time, focusing on good policies, labour-intensive techniques; oriented industries for labour market. Other reasons of unemployment based on the impact of labour union; lawmaking and salary inflexibility Kalim (2003) pointed out the determinants of unemployment and analyzing the numerical association between real growth rate of GDP, population inflation with unemployment as high rate of unemployment is because of population factor, and concluded the majority of labour force remain jobless. Echebiri (2005), highlighted as the determinants of unemployment the fast growth of population growth rate and labor force, education and job preference, poor social and physical infrastructures. According to Akhtar and Shahnaz (2005), the factors of unemployment are associated with investment and low GDP. Schoeman et al. (2008) stated the factors of unemployment are concerned with macro-economic variables, union sation and real exchange as the ratio of recognized employment, crude oil values, banker's receipt rate and capital stock. Eita and (Eita and Ashipala (2010) examined the factors of unemployment focused on macro-economic variables covering through unemployment model and employing Engle and Granger approach to guesstimate the strategy in order to acquire the reality of unemployment . Kingdon and Knight (2001) studied unemployment through probit model the different factors. According to Garcia(2004) as stated the reasons of unemployment. Valadkhani (2003) studied on unemployment through the various components. Monastiriotis (2006) stated as unemployment on the basis of macroeconomic status and employing Keynesian and monetarist domain. Ehrlich (1973) narrated as unemployment enhances crime rate. Low income resorts the individuals to commit crime in society which is related with unemployment due to relatively low. Ehrlich (1973), as explained that unemployment is connected with crime rate and dearth of income opportunities in context of the legal labour market and resorting the individuals to criminal activities. Zaidi (2005) concluded that unemployment problems owing to increasing economic development. (Jamshaid, et al, 2010) unemployment is associated with workforce problem, labor class and professional aptitude and uncertainty and economic problems. According to Benneth (2007) the relationship between fiscal policies is associated with unemployment. Volker (2005) stated as the function of unemployment in the financial development while it is the display of the monetary collapse or fiscal catastrophe. (ILO, 2011), stated for an unemployment as fruitless and drain on society's incomes for unemployed individuals. (Rothiem, 2007) explained as unemployment is concerned with monetary well-being, misconduct, the destruction of socialwealth, desolation and societal uncertainty (Kyei&Gyeke, 2011) explained as Unemployment is as an outcome of monetary contraction, low degrees of financial development.(Ali, 2010) elucidated that unemployment is concerned with the backwardness of agrarian parts and deteriorating rule and directive condition, high inflation ratio of population, energy catastrophe, bad governance defective educational organization, and bottomless in grained bribery. According to Noor et al., (2007) explored out the effect of fiscal development on the unemployment and negative impact of economic growth on the level of unemployment. Ahmed at al. (2011) examined relationship of unemployment with economic growth. Square. Subhan and Hayat (2009), pointed out unemployment is subordinated through instable prices and economic growth. Berument et al. (2008) studied that unemployment is attached with macroeconomic policy shocks. Osinubi (2005) investigated the impact of growth on the unemployment and the poverty. Flaim(1990),examined the population changes and unemployment rate. Alan Krueger and Lawrence Summers (1986a, b) and William Dickens and Lawrence Katz (1986a, b) unemployment is related with wage-theory, and focusing on low i-paid wage and high -paid wage the workers in organization. Peter Blau (1955), explained unemployment is attached with social exchange theory. Kaufman (1984) and Blinder and Choi (1990), pointed out the nature and sources of wage rigidity counted as unemployment. Apart from this, unemployment imparts different negative affect to the state economy in particular and economy in general. (Phulpotoet at., 2012). As Seer (1969), produced a high level of poverty, and inequality. This shows the important role unemployment plays in the process of economic growth. According to Bello (2003), the problem of unemployment has often been an issue of great concern to policy makers, the economists, and economic managers alike; given the overwhelming effect on individuals, the society and the economy at large. Khan, Khattak and Hussain (2012) investigated the inter-relationship of GDP growth and unemployment. Hussain, Siddiqi and Iqbal (2010) traced out the relationship between unemployment and economic growth. Naqvi and Lubna (2002) stated as unemployment is an outcome of women participation at large in economic activities. (Aslam, 2009-10), examined unemployment is related with low growth rate and high rate of population growth. Maqbool, et.al.(2013)investigated that unemployment is

associated with inflation, high populace of foreign direct investment, gross domestic product, inflation, and external debt.

Aim and objectives of the present study

- To investigate the relationship between unemployment and overpopulation in Hyderabad division.
- To explore out the reasonable factors of unemployment in Hyderabad division
- To examine the relationship between quality of education and unemployment in Hyderabad division

Hypothesis

- Overpopulation is likely to be related with unemployment
- Shortage of industries is likely to be related with unemployment
- Quality of education is likely to be related with unemployment

III. Research Methodology

The hypothesis of the presented case study is based on three main parameters including 1. The overpopulation is likely to be related with unemployment, 2. The shortage of industries is likely to be related with unemployment, 3. The quality of education is likely to be related to unemployment. Both independent and dependent variables are considered in the proposed study these are included overpopulation, (independent variables). The dependent variables include unemployment related to the overpopulation. Using hypothesis, the following research methodology is developed for the collection of data and to know the determinants of unemployment in the of Hyderabad district of Sindh province of Pakistan.

In this research, a stratified method of probability sampling is used for collecting the data. The total sample size for this study was 300. A sample size of 300 samples for the different areas of Hyderabad who involved in unemployment, around 260 collected data through the questionnaire from unemployed and other 40 sample selected to social activist and non-government organization who are involved in unemployment and those people who are related to this type of research and also some data collected from people. From this perspective, all knowledge is predicated on the values, ideas, and judgments of the individual, and is locally and contextually defined. The reliability of this scale is 0.84. Data were analyzed with the aid of SPSS Statistics 20.

Table -1 As the table no: 1, indicating that unemployment 50.0 percentages is on account of less economic growth, 8.3 of advance technology while 41.7 numbered as illiteracy rate among the individuals.

These are the Main Reason of Unemployment		
	Frequency	%
Less Economic Growth	150	50.0
Advance in Technology	25	8.3
Illiteracy	125	41.7
Total	300	100.0

Table No- 2 This table showing that unemployment 50.0 percentages is on account of leadership problem, 8.3 of lack of infrastructure and 25.0 numbered as educational policy while 16.7 percentages because of favoritism among the individuals

These Factors are Responsible of Unemployment		
	Frequency	%
Leadership problem	150	50.0
Lack of infrastructure	25	8.3
Educational policy	75	25.0
Favoritism	50	16.7
Total	300	100.0

Table no-3 This table resulting that 58.3 percentages accepted that unemployment is an outcome of overpopulation whereas 41.7 percentages remained rejected in this regard.

Overpopulation is the Cause of Unemployment		
	Frequency	Percent
Yes	175	58.3
No	125	41.7
Total	300	100.0

Regression Analysis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.898 ^a	.806	.805	.63486

a. Predictors: (Constant), overpopulation is the cause of unemployment, which factors are responsible of unemployment?

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	496.961	2	248.480	616.500	.000 ^b
	Residual	119.706	297	.403		
	Total	616.667	299			

a. Dependent Variable: which is the main reason of unemployment?

b. Predictors: (Constant), overpopulation is the specific factor of unemployment and responsible of unemployment

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.629	.112		-5.636	.000

which factors are responsible of unemployment?	.794	.041	.658	19.493	.000
overpopulation is the cause of unemployment	.924	.098	.318	9.413	.000

a. Dependent Variable: what are the main reasons of unemployment

IV. Results and discussions

Such the study resulted as the various determinants of unemployment resorting the individuals to the different stages such as frustration, suicidal action, rude behavior and unsatisfactory life in a society. Besides to this, the individuals of Hyderabad division are educated as well as less educated, but work or job which is available that does not match their positions, and other jobs are given on the basis of nepotisms and favoritisms. Other factors are explored out as less number of factories, overpopulation, and economic growth in economy, poor education the public of human society, bad governance, and low paid practice to workers, job vacancy problems, and obsolete infrastructural systems in Hyderabad Sindh Pakistan.

V. Conclusion

Unemployment is associate with the determinants such as backwardness of agriculture sector, nepotisms and favoritism; obsolete technology; loss in financial sectors, bribery and corruption in job acquisition, mismatch in work and education; low paid system, constant growth of economy, overpopulation, inflation, migration, job vacancy shortage, the nature of job , the change of job, behavior of partner worker in organization; lack of proper training and skill in the respect field of work, family issue, less production and low investment, foreign market attraction, low labor work, force work face and other different determinants which are responsible for unemployment of Hyderabad. As for promotion of such the facts, the government and state take necessary action to improve and develop specific strategies to remove such an issue and set up industries, vocational institutions, job oriented programs and organizations for unemployed individuals of Hyderabad division Sindh Pakistan.

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